

**MECHANISMS OF COMMUNICATION CULTURE FORMATION IN
FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS (BASED ON ENGLISH
LANGUAGE MATERIALS)**

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the mechanisms of communication culture formation in future foreign language teachers. It is known that students can communicate with each other in English in everyday life. They can develop their communication skills in English through exercises and tasks such as sharing ideas, holding discussions, using different specific materials, speaking and listening. In fact, the establishment of a relationship based on mutual respect and trust between the teacher and the student is the main link in the formation of oral communication. The reason is that students learn speech skills and communication culture mainly from pedagogues.

Key words: communication culture, phonetic features, grammatical structures, syntactic divisions, cooperation, listening comprehension, phonetic errors, logical and critical thinking, monologic and dialogical speech, audiovisual and hearing aids, mobilization.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена механизмам формирования культуры общения у будущих учителей иностранного языка (на материале английского языка). Известно, что в повседневной жизни студенты могут общаться друг с другом на английском языке. Они могут развивать свои коммуникативные навыки на английском языке, обмениваясь идеями, проводя дискуссии, используя различные аутентичные материалы, выполняя упражнения и задания, такие как говорение и аудирование. По сути, установление отношений, основанных на взаимном уважении и доверии между учителем и учеником, является основным звеном в формировании устного общения. Причина в том, что речевые навыки и культура общения обучаются в основном у педагогов.

Ключевые слова. культура общения, фонетические особенности, грамматические конструкции, синтаксические деления, сотрудничество, аудирование, фонетические ошибки, логическое и критическое мышление,

монологическая и диалогическая речь, аудиовизуальные и слуховые средства, мобилизовать

The process of development of English communication skills of philology (English) students at a higher educational institution is quite different from other non-philology students. Its specific principles are as follows: mastering the context-based linguistic material in English in future foreign language teachers, improving its quality and summarizing the extent of language material mastery; systematically increasing and combining a number of units of the assimilated English language: developing oral speech in a foreign language by combining various organizational-methodical and pedagogical-psychological components of the effectiveness of communication between students; development of linguistic culture and others.

M.A Snow and D.M. Brinton, a well-known English Methodist, also mentioned the desirability of providing "Content Based Instructions" to students [2; p. 66]. This direction is especially important for future foreign language teachers in the development of communication culture in teaching foreign languages, as well as in the development of oral speech. It encourages learning the language using the content of any subject. This gives the opportunity to encourage students to learn the language meaningfully, to use it as a real communication tool from the first lessons. The main goal is to turn students into independent learners, developing autonomy in the educational process outside the classroom.

The causes of the problems and difficulties in the development of communication culture in English for students of the philological (English) direction of higher educational institutions, the levels of acquisition of the skills of oral communication culture in English, the analysis of knowledge and skills of the students, professor-o' The results of the interview and survey conducted with the participation of teachers show that the problems and difficulties that may arise in this direction are as follows: insufficient lexicon (vocabulary) for the development of communication culture of future specialists, (in the process of communication not fully understanding the content of the conversation when expressing one's thoughts); to logically structure and connect the components of the text (inability to choose words clearly and correctly in the grammatical and syntactic structure of the sentence); homogeneity of syntactic devices (monotony of speech and inability to break out of ready-made speech patterns); violation of intonation (tone) standards; errors such as not being able to correctly use syntactic synonymous means, etc.

As part of our research work, we found it appropriate to study the root causes of various typical mistakes and problems that may arise in the development of communication culture of future foreign language teachers. After all, we all know that it is ineffective to develop the culture of communication among students without studying the true essence of the problem. Below we will analyze the linguistic and psychological aspects of the problem.

We know that in the development of communication culture, the role of psychological components is as important as linguistic aspects. Psychologist I.A. Zimnyaya states that the expression of thought consists of two psychological structures that "surface (form)" and implement, and on the basis of these factors, the role of "speech need" is special: "stimulating factor for speaking and motivating factor for communication this is a speech need" [3; 194 p. 4; p. 14]

The need may arise due to external and internal influences. If the external influence is taken as a student, the internal influence means knowing the mechanisms of speech, i.e. language materials. In order to enter into communication, the existence of a stimulus-stimulating (exclamation) factor and the need is the formation of thought. It is important to know language materials from a psychological point of view as mechanisms of communication. Understanding is formed and developed in the process of communication, and communication in the process of understanding. Also, communication is an important type of speech activity, which causes a number of psychological complications depending on the language and type of speech being learned through it.

Phonetic problems are among the main obstacles in the development of speech skills in the process of listening. R.P. As Milrud points out: "language learners misunderstand words by listening, because of this they hear them incorrectly" [5;96-b 6;47-b] ("lesson" (lesson) - "lessen" (reduce), "material" (information) - "materiel" (military equipment), "accept" - "except" (except for...), "advice" (advice) - "advise" (inform), "complement" (complement each other) - "compliment" (compliment) words. It meant that he can express his opinions in a foreign language by correctly choosing language tools that match the communicative purpose and the content of the speech, and that he understands communication in the same order [5; 68-b].

Through the study of linguistic, psychological and methodical problems and difficulties, as well as the analysis of the results of the conducted experimental work, in our scientific research work, we see the linguistic, psychological, methodical recommendations of the process of developing the communication

culture of students with the integration of factors of student participation. we suggest going out. These aspects will help us to improve the existing system of methodical recommendations in this direction. So, let's summarize these suggestions and recommendations with the help of the following diagram (see Figure 1. 1):

1. Figure 1. 4-step methodical recommendations for the development of communication culture in future foreign language teachers.

Based on the above, we can include the following factors in the successful development of philological students' communication culture in English: linguistic factors; psychological and social factors; methodological components; suggestions for foreign language learners.

So, when the above components are summarized in the educational process, it is possible to optimize the process of developing the English communication culture of students of philological education. Also, the use of these pedagogical factors by teachers of foreign languages, that is, English, in higher educational institutions, and the practical application of the proposed methodical recommendations, in practical training, it is possible not only to develop the

culture of communication, but also to increase the effectiveness of foreign language education. .

CONCLUSION

The development of communication culture in a foreign language depends on the student's ability to regularly work independently and motivation in this process, and their didactic preparation. It is clear from this that it is desirable for the student to demonstrate the abilities of planning, introspection (self-management) and autonomy, that is, for the student to become a full-fledged equal member of the language learning process. In fact, the establishment of a relationship based on mutual respect and trust between a teacher and a student is the main link in the formation of oral communication. The reason is that students learn speech skills and communication culture mainly from pedagogues.

References:

1. Snow, M.A., Briton, D.M. Content-based classroom: New perspectives on integrating language and content (2nd ed). – MI: University of Michigan Press, 2017. – P 66.
2. Зимняя И.А. Лингвопсихология речевой деятельности. – М.: МПСИ, “МОДЭК”, 2001. – 432 с.
3. Леонтьев А.А. Язык реч речевая деятельность. Издательство: “Красанд”, 2010. – 338 с.
4. Мильруд Р. П. Методика преподавания английского языка. English teaching methodology. – М.: “Дрофа”, 2005. – 253 с.
5. Горюного Е. М Развитие коммуникативных способностей студентов вузы при обучении иностранному языку (на примере английского языка). Дис. Канд. Психол. Наук. Тулас. 2004. – 180 с.

